

Tungro (RTV) incidence in direct seeded and transplanted rice

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We compared RTV incidence and density of RTV vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix* spp. in direct seeded and transplanted IR36 and TN1 rice.

In the first experiment Jul-Sep 1986 and Apr-Jun 1987, the nursery for transplanted rice was seeded 3 wk before direct seeded rice was planted. The seedling nursery was prepared near the test field. Data were taken 47 d after transplanting (DT) and seeding (DAS).

In the second experiment Nov-Jan 1986 and Aug-Oct 1987, the nursery for transplanted rice was seeded and direct seeded rice was broadcast at the same time. A small nursery was prepared in each test plot. Data were taken 66 DAS.

Seeding rate of direct seeded rice was 100 kg/ha; spacing of transplanted rice was 20 × 20 cm. Five- × five-m plots were laid out in randomized complete block design with four replications.

RTV symptoms were scored on all plants for transplanted rice and on all plants in ten 20- × 20-cm sampling units for direct seeded rice. Rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and spherical virus (RTSV) incidence were determined by the latex test in 50-100 plants/replicate samples taken in a W-pattern from transplanted rice and in 10-50 plants/sampling unit in direct seeded rice. All plants showing symptoms were tested. GLH density was determined by 10 sweeps of an insect net in each plot.

In both experiments, there were more plants with RTV symptoms and combined RTBV and RTSV incidence in transplanted rice than in direct seeded rice (see table). GLH density was also higher in transplanted rice. □

GLH density, incidence of RTV, RTBV, and RTSV in direct seeded and transplanted IR36 and TN1 rice plants.^a IRRRI, 1986-87 dry and wet seasons.

Cultural method	GLH density (no./10 sweeps)	RTV incidence (%)	Plants (%) infected with			
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
Experiment I ^b						
IR36	Direct seeded	13 ± 8	1 ± 1	1	1	2
	Transplanted	33 ± 15	23 ± 15	64	9	12
TN1	Direct seeded	7 ± 3	6 ± 2	4	3	14
	Transplanted	71 ± 26	96 ± 3	81	1	14
Experiment II ^c						
IR36	Direct seeded	6 ± 2	1 ± 1	2	2	1
	Transplanted	12 ± 3	12 ± 6	29	2	18
TN1	Direct seeded	11 ± 4	19 ± 6	9	6	16
	Transplanted	12 ± 1	80 ± 8	66	2	23

^a± Standard deviation. ^bData taken 47 d after direct seeding or transplanting. ^cData taken 66 d after direct seeding or seedbed seeding.

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) on rice in Madagascar

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RYMV, reported to cause severe economic damage to rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in West Africa, has now been identified in Madagascar.

The disease was observed in Apr 1989 in some fields at Lac Alaotra, the largest contiguous rice-growing area, and in May 1989 in some fields on the Marovoay plains in the northwest. Infected varieties were Makalioka 34, Tche kouai, Boina 1329, and Tsipala.

Naturally infected plants exhibit a bright mottle with chlorotic stripes,

sterility of panicles, and stunting. Regrowth from diseased plants showed a well defined mosaic. When the virus was mechanically transmitted to Angihika, Chianan 8, and Tsipala, the same symptoms developed.

In agar-gel double-diffusion tests, virus in crude extracts from both inoculated and systemically infected leaves reacted strongly with RYMV antiserum obtained from IITA. These tests showed the isolates from Lac Alaotra and Marovoay to be serologically identical.

RYMV is known to be transmitted by Chrysomelidae beetles. *Trichispa sericea* Guérin and *Hispa gestroi* Chapman are considered the most serious insect problem of rice in Madagascar.

Investigations on the vector beetle and the virus are under way in collaboration with FOFIFA. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Stem borer (SB) incidence at different growth stages of rainfed rice

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We compared SB incidence in farmers' fields in shallow water, deepwater, very

deepwater, and flooded rainfed rice environments 1987-88. Rice varieties were Mahsuri, Chakia 59, Jalmagna, and Madhukar, respectively.

Samples of 200 stems were taken in each environment at pre-flood, early elongation, late elongation, and maturity stages. Correlation coefficients calculated for different rice environments and growth stages are